

ing areas of north and northeast Thailand.

During 1981, 12 nonglutinous lines from RD7 mutants plus resistant varieties from India were screened in a

greenhouse at the Rice Protection Research Center, Bangkok, using gall midges from a mass rearing culture. Two RD7 mutants — RD7^{77G} CO-55-3-5-1 and RD7^{77G} CO-77-9-1-1—

were resistant to gall midge (Table 2). All Indian rice varieties except W1263 were susceptible, confirming the results of the International Gall Midge Biotype Collaborative Project. *h*

Evaluation of National Screening Nursery against rice thrips

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National Screening Nursery entries were field tested for resistance to rice thrips

Baliothrips biformis Schmutz at the RRS, Kapurthala. Thirty-five-day-old seedlings of each entry were planted 1 seedling/hill in two 5-m rows. Hills were spaced 15 × 15 cm with 20 cm between rows in each selection and 40 cm between selections. TN1 was included as the susceptible check. Entries were scored for thrips damage 20 days after transplanting (growth

stage 2) by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (1980).

Of 384 entries, 3 were scored 1; 19, 2; 107, 3; 186, 4; 59, 5; 6, 6; and 2, 7. Average score was 4. The 3 entries given a score of 1 (most resistant) were IET8200 (Hansraj/Saket 4), IET8258 (Hema/Vikram/Rajeswari/CR57-1523) and IET8283 (Tellahamsa/CR126-42-5). *h*

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Salt tolerance of mangrove swamp rice varieties

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Development of salt-tolerant rice varieties would help stabilize rice production and make expansion of cultivable land possible in mangrove swamps of West African countries where salinity is a major limiting factor. Studies to develop

improved salt-tolerant varieties adapted to mangrove conditions were started in 1979.

A method to rapidly evaluate rice variety and breeding line salt tolerance by comparing seedling root growth in salin-

Root lengths, root increments, and tolerance ratios (TR) of salt-tolerant and some moderately tolerant mangrove swamp rice varieties^a, Rokupr, Sierra Leone.

Variety	Root length (cm) in culture solution		Root increment (cm)	Root length (cm) in 80 mM NaCl solution		Root increment (cm)	TR
	7 DS	11 DS		13 DS	17 DS		
<i>Tolerant</i>							
Pa Merr 108A	2.9	7.9	5.0	8.6	11.1	2.5	0.50
Pa Foday Yoreh 260	1.3	5.5	4.2	5.9	8.0	2.1	0.50
Gassiline 193B	1.9	6.8	4.9	6.9	9.2	2.3	0.47
Pa Fant 213	1.3	6.7	5.4	7.1	9.3	2.2	0.41
Pa Rice Mill 199	1.9	8.2	6.3	8.5	11.1	2.6	0.41
Pa Bathurst 32A	1.4	4.9	3.5	4.8	6.2	1.4	0.40
Ginsa Killing 408	1.6	7.0	5.4	7.2	9.7	2.5	0.46
Majako 334	4.8	8.5	3.7	8.7	10.4	1.7	0.46
Janeh Kano 469	2.7	6.7	4.0	6.9	8.7	1.8	0.45
Banjul Ba 355	1.8	6.2	4.4	6.5	8.3	1.8	0.41
Kaopa Wolengo 443	3.0	6.5	3.5	7.0	8.4	1.4	0.40
<i>Moderately tolerant</i>							
SR 26 ^b	2.6	7.2	4.6	8.0	9.8	1.8	0.39
BD 2 ^b	2.2	6.9	4.7	7.7	9.5	1.7	0.36
Rok 8 ^b	4.6	7.9	3.3	8.5	9.5	1.0	0.30
Rok 4 ^b	5.0	8.7	3.7	9.4	10.4	1.0	0.27
Rok 5 ^b	3.4	7.9	4.5	8.2	9.4	1.2	0.27
Rok 9 ^b	4.9	8.3	3.4	8.6	9.5	0.9	0.27
Phar Com En ^b	3.2	7.4	4.2	8.2	9.2	1.0	0.24
Atahna 311A	3.8	8.0	4.2	8.2	9.6	1.4	0.33
Pa Sorro 104A	1.8	7.7	5.9	8.8	10.1	1.3	0.22
Nkumbandingo 405	3.5	10.7	7.2	10.9	12.0	1.1	0.15
<i>Checks</i>							
Pokkali (tolerant)	5.5	10.0	4.4	10.2	12.5	2.3	0.52
IR28 (sensitive)	2.0	6.5	4.5	6.4	6.6	0.2	0.04

^aDS = days after sowing. TR = $\frac{\text{root increment over 4 days in salinized culture solution}}{\text{root increment over 4 days in nonsalinized culture solution}}$. ^bRecommended variety.

ized and nonsalinized culture solution was tested, found suitable, and used to screen 510 accessions of traditional varieties from mangrove swamp areas of Sierra Leone, Gambia, and Guinea Bissau.

Root length of seedlings was measured 7 and 11 days after germination. The seedlings were then placed in saline (80 mM NaCl) culture solutions. Root length was measured 13 and 17 days after germination. Salinity tolerance was calculated as the tolerance ratio (TR) of root growth after 4 days in saline solution to root growth after 4 days in non-saline solution.

The TR ranged between -0.46 and

0.52. Because of root shrinkage in saline solution, highly salt-sensitive varieties yielded negative values. Pokkali, the tolerant check, gave the highest TR (0.52). Eleven varieties had TR larger than 0.40 (see table). Forty-six varieties had TR greater than 0.15. They were rated moderately tolerant. The remaining 453 varieties exhibited low tolerance — 342 had TR lower than IR28, the sensitive check variety.

Several varieties recommended for mangrove swamp cultivation were included in the screening. They were all moderately tolerant. Several extensively cultivated local varieties — Pa Sorro (Sierra Leone), Nkumbadingo (Gam-

bia), and Atahna (Guinea-Bissau) — were also moderately tolerant.

Results show most traditional swamp varieties have little or no salinity tolerance. Findings suggest that mangrove swamp rice cultivation has avoided high salinity periods. Transplanting is delayed until salt dissipates at the beginning of the season and cultivation is limited to areas where the crop can mature before salt returns.

Results indicated that if new varieties with better salt tolerance were developed, expansion into marginal areas could result. ✎

Pest management and control DISEASES

Morphology and serological relationship of grassy stunt-associated filamentous nucleoprotein and rice stripevirus

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The rice stripe virus (StV), transmitted by planthopper *Laodelphax striatellus*, is a branched filament. Filamentous particles are also found in grassy stunt (RGS)-infected rice leaves. StV particles and rice grassy stunt (GSV)-associated filamentous particles (GSV-f) are similar in morphology.

Purified GSV-f and StV were stained with uranium acetate and examined in an electron microscope. GSV-f had a circular filament, 6-8 nm in diameter and 1,000-3,000 nm long (Fig. 1a). StV had a circular helix 11-13 nm in diameter that varied in length (Fig. 1b). The loosened helix was a coiled filament 6-8 nm in diameter.

The serological relationship between GSV-f and StV was examined in precipitin ring interface and agar gel diffusion tests. In the ring interface test purified GSV-f reacted with diluted anti-GSV-f serum up to 1/1,280. It re-

1. a. Electron micrograph of rice grassy stunt-associated filamentous particles (X120,000). b. Electron micrograph of rice stripe virus (X120,000).

2. Agar gel diffusion test with purified grassy stunt-associated filamentous particles (G) and rice stripe virus (S), and their antisera (Gs and Ss, respectively).

acted with anti-StV serum up to 1/80 dilution. Purified StV reacted with diluted StV serum up to 1/1,280 and with anti-GSV-f serum up to 1/20. Fractions purified from virus-free rice

leaves reacted weakly with both sera at 1/10.

In the agar gel diffusion test, 0.8% agar gel containing 0.1% SDS was used. Two bands, one distinct and one faint,